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List of abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation or acronym	Full name or phrase
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AOE	Action-Oriented Experiment
CB	Capacity building
DEI	Diversity, Equity and Inclusion
DG Research or DG RTD	Directorate-General for Research and Innovation
EC	European Commission
ERA	European Research Area
EU	European Union
FP10	10th EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation
GA	Grant Agreement
GBA+	Gender-Based Analysis Plus
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GEP	Gender Equality Plan
GIA	Gender Impact Assessment
GILL	Gendered Innovation Living Labs
GRSIE	Gender-Responsive Smart Innovation and Entrepreneurship
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
LL	Living Labs
OI	Open Innovation
QH	Quadruple Helix
REA	Research Executive Agency
RRF	Recovery and Resilience Facility
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
R&I	Research and Innovation
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprise
SPARK	Self-assessment tool mentioned in monitoring context
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package

GILL consortium

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Executive summary

Purpose and objectives of Policy Development Report

This **Policy Development Report** is the culminating strategic output of the GILL project, translating conceptual work and analytical foundations into a coherent set of **evidence-based policy directions** to advance **gender-responsive innovation** within the European Research and Innovation (R&I) ecosystem. Building on the methodological and strategic orientations established in the **Strategy Planning for Policy Development (Deliverable 4.2)**, the report aims to consolidate findings generated through **Action-Oriented Experimentations (AOEs)**, **impact evaluation** and **stakeholder engagement** into an operational framework capable of informing EU, national and regional policy agendas.

The report pursues the overarching objective of embedding **Gender-Responsive Smart Innovation and Entrepreneurship (GRSIE)** into the governance, culture and practices of innovation ecosystems. It does so by articulating **the Cultural Fix** as a necessary complement to the traditional ‘three fixes’ of Gendered Innovations, thus highlighting the need to address underlying **norms, values** and **behavioural dynamics** that shape innovation processes.

Ultimately, the report provides policymakers and practitioners with a structured roadmap that supports **systemic transformation**, facilitates the uptake of gender-responsive tools and strengthens alignment with **Horizon Europe**, the **European Research Area (ERA)** and the **EU Gender Equality Strategy**.

Summary of policy recommendations

The policy recommendations presented aim to foster gender equality, inclusiveness and intersectional awareness across research, innovation and institutional contexts. They are structured into five thematic areas: **Cross-Cutting Recommendations**, **Digital Innovation Ecosystems**, **Green Transition and Sustainability**, **Health Innovation**, and **Institutional and Cultural Transformation Tools**.

Cross-cutting recommendations focus on embedding participatory methodologies such as Living Labs and the Cultural Fix model into Gender Equality Plans (GEPs), aligning Horizon Europe and ERA frameworks, institutionalising reflexive governance, incentivising leadership commitment and establishing harmonised monitoring systems. These measures ensure that gender equality becomes a dynamic, evidence-based driver of institutional innovation rather than a compliance requirement.

Recommendations for digital innovation ecosystems emphasise mandatory gender impact assessments for AI and ICT projects, the adoption of inclusive design standards, targeted training for developers and engineers, and interdisciplinary collaboration to mitigate bias and ensure fair, representative digital products.

For the green transition, policies advocate systematic gender and intersectional impact assessments for climate and energy projects, alongside dedicated support for women-led green entrepreneurship through funding, mentorship and visibility initiatives.

In health innovation, recommendations call for the integration of sex- and gender-sensitive research methodologies, cross-disciplinary collaboration and targeted programmes to support women innovators and leaders, ensuring equitable outcomes and participation in health R&I.

Finally, institutional and cultural transformation tools stress the importance of reflexivity, co-creation and continuous learning mechanisms, enabling organisations to embed inclusivity into everyday practices, track progress through mixed-method monitoring and scale effective gender-responsive interventions across contexts.

Collectively, these recommendations offer actionable strategies for institutions, policymakers and stakeholders to drive systemic and sustainable change, ensuring that gender equality and inclusiveness are at the heart of innovation excellence, organisational culture and research impact.

Strategic contributions to EU gender equality policy

The report contributes directly to the advancement of key EU policy frameworks. It operationalises the commitments of the **EU Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025**, strengthens the implementation of **ERA Action 5** on inclusiveness and gender equality, and reinforces **Horizon Europe's** cross-cutting ambition to integrate gender in research content, organisational structures and funding eligibility.

Through its empirical validation of GRSIE and the Cultural Fix, GILL provides a **novel, actionable framework** that complements existing regulatory measures by addressing **cultural, symbolic** and **behavioural** dimensions of inequality often overlooked in traditional policy approaches. This positions GILL as a strategic contributor to the EU's transition toward more **inclusive, responsible** and **socially sustainable** innovation models.

Overview of methodology and sources

The evidence base informing this report was generated through a robust and validated methodological process combining **participatory, intersectional** and **iterative** approaches.

Fifteen **Action-Oriented Experimentations (AOEs)** were conducted across eight European countries in real organisational settings, applying GILL tools such as **Fair Meetings, Hear the Right Voices, Reflective Diaries** and **GenderMag** to assess their capacity to support cultural and institutional transformation. These experimentations provided rich empirical evidence on gender dynamics, organisational behaviour and practical barriers to inclusiveness.

A structured **impact evaluation**, complemented by **process evaluation**, measured the effectiveness, usability and transferability of GILL methodologies, identifying enabling conditions, organisational challenges and systemic patterns across diverse contexts.

Parallel to experimentation, nearly 30 **stakeholder interviews at the EU level** and additional consultations in the United States were conducted across the Quadruple Helix, gathering perspectives from academia, industry, civil society and policymaking. These interviews revealed structural inequalities, gaps in policy literacy, and opportunities for strengthening gender-responsive innovation through systemic and cultural interventions.

Finally, validation and **triangulation activities** ensured the coherence, relevance and reliability of results, enabling the formulation of robust policy recommendations grounded in practical evidence and cross-sectoral insights.

Introduction

EU policies on gender and innovation

Strategic context and evolution of EU policy approaches

Gender equality, diversity and inclusion have become defining priorities within the European policy landscape, shaping not only the social and legal framework but also innovation agendas. The European Union has progressively strengthened its commitment to gender equality through legislative directives, soft-law frameworks, EU mainstreaming mechanisms and a set of strategic, sector-specific policies.

Gender equality is a cross-cutting priority in the EU's major R&I frameworks **Horizon 2020**, **Horizon Europe** and the renewed **European Research Area (ERA)**. These frameworks have progressively integrated gender mainstreaming into research funding, governance and evaluation mechanisms; thus, it requires organisations to integrate gender equality plans (GEPs) as an eligibility condition and to consider gender dimension in project design and implementation. This has resulted in new organisational governance structures, staffing reforms and the development of inclusive research practices. The introduction of **Gender Equality Plans (GEPs)** as a formal eligibility criterion for funding under Horizon Europe represents a decisive step towards institutionalising equality.

A turning point in the EU's approach came with the **Gendered Innovations** initiative, coordinated by Stanford University. This pioneering project demonstrated, through empirical evidence and methodological tools, how sex, gender and intersectional analysis can enhance the robustness and societal relevance of research and innovation outcomes. It articulated three complementary strategies for systemic change:

- **Fix the Numbers:** Increase women's participation and representation.
- **Fix the Institutions:** Address structural barriers and promote organisational transformation.
- **Fix the Knowledge:** Integrate gender and intersectional analysis into research content and design.

Despite these advances, implementation remains uneven. While policy awareness is high among gender experts, many R&I stakeholders still perceive gender equality as peripheral to scientific or technological priorities. Persistent conceptual ambiguities, limited dissemination of effective tools, and weak monitoring mechanisms continue to constrain progress.

Making gender equality institutional in R&I

The EU's **Research Framework Programmes (FPs)** have played a central role in embedding gender perspectives into the European R&I ecosystem:

- **FP5 (1998-2002)** established the foundation by addressing women's employment, health and social inclusion.
- **FP6 (2002-2006)** integrated gender analysis into research methodologies, improving awareness of gendered knowledge production.
- **FP7 (2007-2013)** linked gender equality to the principles of the **European Research Area (ERA)**, reinforcing collaboration and shared responsibility.
- **Horizon 2020 (2014-2020)** extended the scope by introducing gender-sensitive research design and promoting gender balance in leadership and participation.

Horizon Europe (2021-2027) consolidated this trajectory by formalising **Gender Equality Plans** as an eligibility condition for participation and embedding **intersectional analysis** as a guiding principle. GEPs serve as practical instruments for structural change, requiring organisations to establish measurable objectives, targeted actions and monitoring systems to advance gender equity. The **2025–2027 Horizon Europe Strategic Plan** reinforces this approach by consolidating gender equality as a cross-cutting priority embedded within missions, clusters and partnerships. It also connects gender equality, diversity and inclusion considerations to major societal transformations – climate neutrality, digitalisation, health and strategic autonomy.

Nevertheless, as the programme reaches its midterm review, concerns have been raised regarding the next cycle (**Horizon Europe 2028-2034**). While formal requirements such as the GEP criterion appear likely to remain, preliminary documents suggest limited ambition for strengthening implementation or evaluation. Without robust monitoring, there is a risk that GEPs could become procedural checkboxes rather than a mechanism for transformative change.

Integrating gender into broader EU policy instruments

The **Next Generation EU** and its core instrument, the **Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF)**, were established in response to the social and economic impacts of the Covid-19 pandemic. Gender equality is defined as a **horizontal principle** within the RRF Regulation, requiring Member States to demonstrate how their national recovery and resilience plans contribute to gender equality across six policy pillars.

The inclusion of gender provisions in the RRF represents a significant political achievement for gender mainstreaming. However, variations in national implementation and limited monitoring capacities have raised concerns about the consistency and effectiveness of these measures across Member States.

The **EU Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025** positions equality as a core value that is fundamental to build a resilient, competitive and democratic Europe. It emphasises dismantling structural barriers, tackling stereotypes, narrowing gender gaps in labour market, increasing women's participation in decision-making and embedding gender perspectives across policy domains.

It adopts a **dual-track approach**, combining targeted measures with systematic gender mainstreaming, and it applies an **intersectional lens** to address overlapping forms of discrimination (Debusscher, 2022). Independent assessments (González Gago & Castellanos Serrano, 2025) underline its strategic value but also call for stronger monitoring and a clearer legal basis post-2025.

- In the **digital domain**, the Strategy aims to address persistent gender imbalances where women represent only 17 % of ICT students and 36 % of STEM graduates in the EU (Eurostat, 2018) and to counter gender bias in emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence (Criado Perez, 2019).
- Within the **green transition**, it highlights gendered impacts of environmental and energy policies, noting that women face higher exposure to energy and transport poverty yet show stronger engagement with sustainability efforts (Sansone, 2021).
- In **health**, it emphasises gender-specific risks, particularly in sexual and reproductive health, calling for gender-sensitive innovation in medical research and healthcare systems (Ingleby, 2017; Franklin et al., 2021).
- In **entrepreneurship**, it recognises persistent disparities in access to finance, networks and visibility, urging reforms to promote diverse and inclusive models of innovation (Ahl & Marlow, 2012; Pettersson et al., 2017).

Persistent gaps and emerging challenges

Despite mature policy architecture, persistent inequalities remain. Women and under-represented groups continue to face barriers in accessing STEM careers, entrepreneurship pathways, innovation management roles and financial capital. This results in a 'leaky pipeline' affecting representation and retention across the innovation ecosystem. These gaps also vary significantly across Member States and sectors, demonstrating that policy ambitions alone are not sufficient.

Several structural and cultural challenges persist:

- Uneven engagement of R&I practitioners compared to gender policy experts
- Conceptual ambiguities surrounding 'gender-responsive innovation'
- Limited dissemination of effective tools and practices across sectors
- Insufficient monitoring and evaluation mechanisms.

These limitations reveal the need for a **systemic and transformative approach** that reconfigures innovation practices and values to achieve true gender responsiveness (Verloo, 2018; Schiebinger & Schraudner, 2011).

As of 2025, the **Gender Equality Strategy 2026–2030** is undergoing public consultation. The research and innovation community has called for maintaining and reinforcing existing commitments, particularly the GEP eligibility criterion, a 50 % gender balance in advisory bodies and stronger provisions on gender-based violence and harassment within R&I environments.

Linkage to the strategy planning for policy development and the GILL Strategy Planning for Policy Development

The EU policy framework on gender and innovation has evolved from fragmented measures into a coherent system combining regulation, incentives and mainstreaming. Yet, implementation remains uneven. To fulfil its ambition of a gender-responsive innovation ecosystem, the EU must further **strengthen monitoring and evaluation**, enhance **institutional accountability** and promote **cross-sectoral collaboration** between gender experts, researchers and innovation actors.

Through its analytical and capacity-building activities, the GILL project contributes to this ongoing transformation, identifying pathways to align competitiveness with social justice and ensuring that Europe's innovation future is inclusive, fair and sustainable.

This *Report on Policy Development* builds directly upon the conceptual, analytical and strategic foundations established in the GILL project, mainly in its **Strategy Planning for Policy Development** (Deliverable 4.2). While Strategy Planning provided the conceptual framework for structuring the policy development pathway within GILL, this report translates those strategic directions into **concrete actions, validated insights and policy recommendations**. In this sense, Strategy Planning represented a preparatory and guiding milestone, whereas Policy Development constitutes its operational and outcome-oriented continuation within the broader **GILL Policy Development Strategy**.

In the Strategy Planning for Policy Development, the GILL consortium articulated a comprehensive understanding of the **challenges and opportunities** surrounding gender equality in innovation and entrepreneurship. It mapped the European Union's evolving commitment to gender equality, from the progressive institutionalisation of **Gender Equality Plans (GEPs)** in *Horizon Europe*, to the integration of the gender dimension within the *Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF)* and the *EU Gender Equality Strategy*. This contextual analysis established a robust policy baseline, enabling the identification of both achievements and persistent gaps in the mainstreaming of gender equality across European innovation systems.

Despite these efforts, Europe continues to **substantially underutilise female talent** in innovation and entrepreneurship. The GILL project has identified that beyond structural barriers – such as insufficient work-life balance policies or limited access to financial and professional resources – **gender stereotypes and unconscious biases** represent the most persistent obstacles to integrating women's needs, perspectives and contributions into innovation processes. These stereotypes, deeply embedded in social institutions, shape perceptions, attitudes and behaviours, thereby reproducing unequal power dynamics across all levels of the innovation ecosystem.

For example, in the domain of **digital transformation**, women often encounter biases related to a presumed lack of technical or leadership skills, which limits their access to funding, recruitment or advancement opportunities. Likewise, in **entrepreneurship**, the prevailing masculine bias associates success with competitiveness, risk-taking and profit orientation – attributes which are historically detached from feminine-coded behaviours. This results in the **systematic undervaluation and marginalisation of women-led ventures**, perceived as less ambitious or less aligned with dominant economic paradigms.

Moreover, GILL highlighted a widespread **lack of gender sensitivity** across innovation ecosystems. The dissemination of information about gender equality and its collective benefits remains insufficient and existing tools, measures or good practices tackling gender issues are often unknown or inaccessible to relevant stakeholders. Consequently, gender equality continues to be perceived primarily as a 'women's issue', rather than as a **societal and systemic value** that benefits all genders and strengthens innovation.

Within this analytical framework, D4.2 also introduced the **Plan of GILL Actions for Policy Development**, a structured and phased roadmap that now guides the design and validation of the policy recommendations presented in this report. The plan was conceived in **three main phases**:

- (i) **Establishing** the theoretical and analytical foundation for **Gender-Responsive and Sustainable Innovation Ecosystems (GRSIE)**.
- (ii) Empirically **evaluating GILL's experimentations** to assess the enhancement of gender responsiveness at individual, organisational and institutional levels.
- (iii) **Translating empirical evidence into policy-relevant insights and actionable recommendations.**

Building upon these phases, the present deliverable makes the methodological and strategic orientations it operative outlined in D4.2. It consolidates empirical evidence gathered through experimentation and stakeholder engagement, analyses its implications for policy design, and formulates **evidence-based recommendations** aimed at embedding gender equality within innovation and entrepreneurship ecosystems.

Ultimately, the linkage between the two steps of the process (Strategy Planning for Policy Development and Policy Development in itself) reflects the **internal coherence and progressive development** of GILL's Policy Development Strategy – from conceptual design to empirical validation and finally to policy formulation. Together, these deliverables constitute a unified trajectory that reinforces GILL's overarching ambition: to advance **gender-responsive, culturally inclusive and socially sustainable innovation across Europe**.

Overview of GILL's policy vision and cultural fix approach

The policy vision developed within GILL stems from the recognition that **structural reforms and quantitative measures** are **not sufficient alone** to achieve lasting gender equality. While increasing women's participation ('fixing the numbers') and reforming institutions ('fixing the institutions') are critical, these efforts must be complemented by a **transformative cultural shift** that reshapes the underlying values, norms and behaviours driving innovation systems.

Accordingly, D4.2 introduced the **Cultural Entrepreneurial Ecosystem** model, which expands upon the Gendered Innovations framework by adding a fourth strategic axis: **'fixing the culture'**. This new dimension complements the previous approaches of:

- **Fixing the numbers**, by increasing women's participation in innovation and entrepreneurship.
- **Fixing the institutions**, by promoting structural changes that support inclusive equality.
- **Fixing the knowledge**, by integrating gender analysis into research and innovation.

Fixing the culture, adds to the previous three approaches by addressing the cultural, behavioural and symbolic dimensions that underpin gender disparities.

The **'fix the culture'** approach embodies GILL's distinctive contribution to the policy debate on gender equality in innovation. It recognises that gender stereotypes are embedded in social and organisational institutions, shaping both individual and collective practices. Consequently, sustainable gender equality can only be achieved by transforming the cultural and social norms that determine how roles, expectations and success are defined and valued.

An integral element of this cultural perspective is the **inclusion of masculinities**, an often overlooked but essential aspect in the pursuit of gender fairness. GILL argues that gender equality must involve all both men and women and that engaging men as active participants in the transformation of norms and behaviours is key to dismantling systemic inequalities. This inclusive vision repositions gender equality as a **shared societal responsibility**, not a women-centric agenda.

Furthermore, GILL's policy vision highlights the importance of strengthening **gender sensitivity** within innovation ecosystems. This requires enhancing awareness, visibility and accessibility of gender-related knowledge, tools and good practices among all relevant stakeholders, such as public authorities, academia, businesses, investors and intermediaries. It also entails demonstrating that gender equality generates tangible benefits for innovation outcomes, competitiveness and sustainability.

Inclusivity should not be understood as the mere absorption of diversity into pre-existing structures, where difference is tolerated only insofar as it fits the established system. It requires a critical examination and transformation of the system itself, allowing it to adapt, evolve and benefit from the richness of multiple perspectives. By embracing diverse experiences, identities and ways of thinking, a system can respond more effectively to a wider range of needs, aspirations and desires, creating environments that are not only fairer but also more innovative, resilient and dynamic. In this sense, inclusivity is a process of co-evolution, where both individuals and structures grow through mutual adaptation.

Through this multidimensional approach, GILL promotes a comprehensive and **ecosystemic understanding** of gender equality. The project recognises that entrepreneurial environments are composed of interdependent **cultural, institutional and behavioural factors**, which can either facilitate or hinder gender equality. Therefore, fostering inclusive and gender-responsive innovation requires aligning these elements through targeted policy actions, educational programmes, institutional reforms and cultural interventions.

Ultimately, GILL's **'fix the culture'** approach does not only aim to correct gender imbalances; it seeks to **transform innovation itself** by redefining the principles of excellence, leadership and success through inclusivity, diversity and social responsibility.

By making these insights into concrete tools, practices and policy mechanisms that support **Gender-Responsive Smart Innovation and Entrepreneurship**, GILL contributes to shaping a new European paradigm of **cultural innovation**, where equality becomes both a moral imperative and a driver of creative and sustainable growth.

Methodological notes on evidence gathering and stakeholder engagement

The methodological approach and the subsequent policy recommendations build upon a structured process of **qualitative evidence gathering and stakeholder engagement**, designed to ensure that GILL's policy outputs are both empirically grounded and contextually relevant. The evidence collection process was conceived as a participatory exercise aimed at capturing the **perceptions, experiences and expectations** of diverse actors involved in innovation and entrepreneurship ecosystems, particularly those operating within Living Labs and hubs active in the areas of **health and resilience, green transition and digital transformation**.

Purpose and scope of evidence gathering

The core aim of the methodology for implementation was to generate **evidence-based insights** to inform the design of **Gender-Responsive and Sustainable Innovation Ecosystems (GRSIE)**.

This was achieved through a set of semi-structured interviews targeting both **stakeholders and policymakers** across the European innovation landscape. The interviews were designed to collect qualitative data on current practices, institutional behaviours and policy frameworks shaping gender equality in innovation, as well as to explore the **structural and cultural barriers** that hinder women's participation in entrepreneurial and research domains.

The interviews sought to illuminate four key dimensions of inquiry:

- The degree of **awareness and integration** of gender equality principles in innovation policies and lab activities.
- The extent to which organisations collect and use **gender-disaggregated data** to inform decision-making.
- The **existing initiatives and resources** devoted to supporting gender-balanced participation and leadership in innovation.
- The **emerging needs and expectations** for future gender-responsive actions and policies.

In line with GILL's overall vision, the methodology adopted a **dialogical, inclusive and multi-actor approach**, ensuring that voices from the **quadruple helix** – academia, industry, government and citizens – were equally represented in the data collection process.

Stakeholder selection and interview process

Structural change requires mechanisms that can translate policy into practice, adapt to contextual realities and engage diverse communities in the innovation process. In this context, the GILL project approach and some of initiatives provided by the project implementation, such as the Living Labs, offer a unique operational environment to bring EU policy ambition to life. As user-centred, open innovation ecosystems embedded in real-life settings, Living Labs are designed to mobilise diverse stakeholders, integrate community knowledge and co-create solutions that reflect real social needs.

Living Labs can translate high-level objectives, in terms of gender equality, diversity and inclusion, into concrete, iterative practices, building the conditions for cultural, organisational and systemic transformation. Because they operate at the intersection of policy, research, industry and society, Living Labs can both implement and shape equality-driven innovation agendas. They serve as territorial brokers, strengthening capacity at local and regional levels while ensuring alignment with European priorities. In doing so, they create

the structural link needed between abstract policy commitments and on-the-ground transformation.

Thus, Living Labs represent a strategic operational infrastructure that can advance gender equality and diversity within European innovation. Their ability to deploy gender-responsive approaches in real contexts strengthens the EU's capacity to foster inclusive, sustainable and socially relevant innovation ecosystems.

The consortium partners collectively identified potential interviewees and organisations representing the diversity of actors operating within innovation ecosystems. Stakeholders were prioritised based on their active involvement in **Living Labs, innovation hubs or policy design processes** relevant to GILL's thematic areas. Given time and resource constraints, each partner was invited to conduct **two in-depth interviews**, ensuring coverage of all four stakeholder categories.

A shared **stakeholder mapping file** was used to coordinate the selection process and avoid overlapping.

The interview process followed a harmonised protocol developed under the coordination of FGB, ensuring methodological consistency and compliance with **GILL's ethical standards**. Prior to each interview, participants received detailed information regarding the purpose of the study, data protection measures and their rights as respondents. **Informed consent** was obtained for all interviews, either electronically or in written form, in compliance with the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

Interviews were **audio-recorded** with the respondent's permission and data was subsequently **anonymised** following the naming convention established in the methodological guide (TYPE OF STAKEHOLDER_RESPONDENT NUMBER_PARTNER ACRONYM_AREA). This ensured full confidentiality and traceability within the GILL consortium while protecting individual identities. Each partner stored recordings and templates in **password-protected folders**, in accordance with the project's ethical and data management protocols.

Analytical framework and data processing

Following each interview, partners completed a **standardised analytical template** to synthesise the collected information and capture key quotations, observations and thematic insights. Templates were filled out in English to facilitate cross-analysis across partners and thematic areas. This harmonised format enabled a systematic examination of patterns and divergences emerging from different national and sectoral contexts.

The analytical framework was designed to support both **vertical** (by thematic area) and **horizontal** (by stakeholder type) analyses. This dual approach allowed GILL to identify not only cross-cutting barriers and enablers of gender equality but also to highlight **sector-specific challenges and promising practices** in the health, green and digital innovation domains.

Interview content and thematic focus

The semi-structured interview guides, developed collaboratively by FGB and ENOLL, included **two sets of questions**: one targeting **stakeholders** and another focusing on **policymakers**. Both sets explored:

- Awareness of the EU's evolving commitment to gender equality in innovation (e.g. the role of DG Research, ERA and DEI initiatives).
- Collection and utilisation of **gender-disaggregated data**.
- Inclusion of **gender perspectives in innovation practices, programmes and policies**.
- Existing or planned **initiatives to promote gender balance** (e.g. quotas, gender-sensitive procurement and tailored training).
- Identification of **sector-specific barriers and opportunities** for women innovators and entrepreneurs.

The policymakers' interviews also addressed the **integration of gender in policy design**, assessment of past and ongoing measures, and the development of **social impact indicators** incorporating gender dimensions. This dual perspective ensured that GILL's policy recommendations could have been informed both by the lived experiences of practitioners and by the strategic insights of policymakers shaping innovation agendas

at the European and national levels.

Outcomes of the evidence-gathering process

The adopted structured methodology ensured the **comparability, transparency and validity** of the collected evidence. By engaging a diverse range of actors across the quadruple helix, GILL was able to triangulate perspectives and capture the **complex interplay between institutional, cultural and behavioural factors** influencing gender responsiveness in innovation ecosystems.

This participatory and ethically robust process forms the empirical foundation of the policy analysis and recommendations elaborated in this report. It directly informs the formulation of actionable measures aimed at **enhancing gender responsiveness, fostering inclusive innovation cultures and embedding the ‘fix the culture’ approach** into the broader GILL Policy Development Strategy.

Table 1. Overview of methodological phases and stakeholder engagement

Phase	Objective	Main activities	Partners involved	Outputs/evidence collected
1. Preparation and coordination	Define methodological framework and ethical standards for data collection	Drafting of interview guide; stakeholder mapping; ethical clearance; shared templates	FGB, ENoLL, all consortium partners	Common methodology, approved interview guide, stakeholder list
2. Stakeholder identification and selection	Ensure diversity and representativeness across the quadruple helix and thematic areas	Identification and selection of interviewees (academia, industry, government, citizens)	Consortium partners in each country	Finalised list of respondents by sector and area
3. Evidence gathering through interviews	Collect insights on gender equality in innovation ecosystems	Conducting semi-structured interviews in Health, Green and Digital areas	Living Lab managers, entrepreneurs, researchers, policymakers	Recorded and anonymised interviews; informed consent forms
4. Data processing and analysis	Systematise and interpret collected qualitative evidence	Completion of analytical templates; thematic coding and synthesis	All interviewers, coordinated by FGB	Analytical templates; sectoral and cross-sectoral findings
5. Validation and integration	Consolidate findings for policy design	Cross-analysis of patterns; identification of barriers, enablers and good practices	Policy team and impact, exploitation, dissemination and communication leaders	Empirical evidence base informing policy recommendations

Gender equality, diversity and inclusion: the role of Living Labs in policy development

Gendered innovation and organisational change in Living Labs

Innovation processes are neither neutral nor universally inclusive.

Evidence shows that gendered norms, unequal access to resources and structural power imbalances shape how problems are framed, whose experiences are prioritised and which solutions are developed and scaled. As applied innovation ecosystems grounded in user-centred and participatory methodologies, Living Labs are strategically positioned to address these biases and advance gender-responsive innovation cultures.

Living Labs should adopt Gendered Innovation Frameworks and principles to ensure that gender perspectives are embedded across the entire innovation life cycle. The GILL project illustrates this through the concept of Gender-Responsive Smart Innovation and Entrepreneurship (GRSIE), which redefines innovation to be 'smart' only when it is responsive to diverse needs and promotes equitable outcomes.

To operationalise this shift, Living Labs should:

- Integrate approaches that acknowledge **gender as a dynamic, intersectional factor** influencing innovation needs and impacts.
- Recognise diverse end-users as legitimate knowledge actors, where **women and under-represented communities shape priority-setting, solution design and evaluation**.
- **Strengthen organisational capacity** to identify and mitigate gendered biases embedded in internal routines, leadership behaviour and collaborative processes.
- **Strategic use of gender-responsive tools and facilitation methods** within Living Labs, can demonstrate how incremental yet structured adaptations in meeting practices, stakeholder selection, team reflection and decision-making can activate deeper cultural and organisational change.

This positions **Living Labs** not only as **innovation infrastructures or co-creation spaces**, but as **learning environments** where organisations experiment with and institutionalise more inclusive modes of governance, collaboration, innovation and entrepreneurship.

Living Lab methodology supporting gender equality, diversity and inclusion

By design, the Living Lab methodology is highly aligned with gender equality, diversity and inclusion goals. Living Labs are user-centred, open innovation ecosystems based on a systematic user co-creation approach, integrating research and innovation processes in real-life communities and settings.¹

Living Labs are structured around six defining characteristics: active user involvement, a multi-method approach, multi-stakeholder participation, orchestration, co-creation and real-life experimentation, each of which can directly reinforce gender-responsive practices.

How can Living Lab characteristics drive gender equality, diversity and inclusion, and integration?

- **Active user involvement:** Living Labs must ensure that user engagement reflects the diversity of actual and potential users, including women and under-represented or marginalised groups. Their lived experiences should inform needs identification, experimentation and evaluation.

¹ ENoLL (2025). Living Lab origins, developments, and future perspectives. <https://zenodo.org/records/14764597>.

- **Multi-method approach:** Combining qualitative, quantitative, creative and participatory methods enables Living Labs to identify gendered needs that standard market or technical research may overlook. Triangulation strengthens validity and enables intersectional analysis.
- **Multi-stakeholder participation:** Living Labs convene quadruple-helix actors (industry, public sector, academia and research, civil society). This broadens the governance base, ensuring that gender considerations are articulated by a diversity of perspectives and legitimised across sectors.
- **Orchestration:** The orchestrator role characterises Living Labs, coordinates diverse actors and mediates power relations. This role is essential for creating safe, equitable spaces, ensuring transparency and facilitating inclusive decision-making.
- **Co-creation:** Co-creation practices elevate experience-based knowledge, value non-dominant forms of expertise and ensure that innovation pathways reflect diverse priorities, not only those of institutions or market actors.
- **Real-life experimentation:** Innovation is deployed in authentic settings, making it possible to observe gender-differentiated experiences, barriers, preferences and usage patterns that scripted testing would fail to capture.

Embedding gender equality, diversity and inclusion across Living Lab layers

Living Labs operate across three interconnected layers: Macro (Living Lab constellation consisting of organised stakeholders (PPP-partnership)); Meso (Living Lab innovation projects); and Micro (Living Lab methodology consisting of different research steps).

Figure 1: *The Structure of Living Labs: A Three-Layered Model*

Source: ENOLL (2025). Living Lab origins, developments, and future perspectives. <https://zenodo.org/records/14764597>.

Living Labs, therefore, should mainstream gender equality, diversity and inclusion at each level:

- At the Macro Level, through the implementation of Gender Equality Plans, ensuring gender-balanced leadership, allocating resources for gender equality, diversity and inclusion implementation.
- At the Meso Level, embedding inclusive design practices, intersectional stakeholder mapping, gender-sensitive and gender-disaggregated data collection.
- At the Micro Level, applying day-to-day methods that enhance equitable participation, visibility and influence.

Taken together, these characteristics and layers make Living Lab well-suited to act as operational engines for gender-responsive transformation, aligning with wider EU strategies on inclusive innovation, industrial competitiveness and cohesion.

From practice to policy

Living Labs sit at the interface between innovation practice and broader public policy goals. They are uniquely placed to mobilise communities, test solutions in real settings, orchestrate multisectoral actors and generate context-rich insights. This positions them as strategic infrastructures for implementing, informing and refining gender-responsive innovation policy.

Accordingly, Living Lab should:

- **Act as policy test beds for gender-responsive innovation governance.**

Living Labs are realistic environments where gender-mainstreaming frameworks, inclusive governance models and participatory decision-making processes are stress-tested under real operational conditions. By experimenting with different approaches to representation, power sharing and accountability, Living Labs can identify the practical enablers and barriers that influence uptake of gender-responsive governance. This generates actionable evidence on what works, for whom and under which conditions. Findings can subsequently inform the adaptation of gender policies to ensure they are implementable, context-appropriate and reflective of the needs of diverse user groups.

- **Operationalise EU gender equality strategies through contextualised approaches integrated within Living Lab governance, project design and stakeholder processes.**

Although EU gender strategies define the overarching principles, their implementation depends on local structures, cultural norms and stakeholder configuration. Living Labs can translate these strategies into practice by embedding gender considerations within governance arrangements, project design and day-to-day collaboration processes. This allows Gender Equality Plans and other frameworks to move from formal compliance to active organisational change. Through facilitation, monitoring and iterative learning, Living Labs support the internalisation of inclusive behaviours while aligning local innovation ecosystems with European standards.

- **Translate high-level policy objectives into actionable methods by adapting stakeholder engagement, co-creation formats and data practices to local needs and organisational contexts.**

Policies frequently articulate ambitious inclusion goals but sometimes operational pathways are less clear. Living Labs can bridge this gap by adapting co-creation methodologies, stakeholder engagement formats and data collection practices to local needs and organisational capacities. This may include tailored outreach to under-represented communities, redesigning workshops to ensure equal participation, and integrating gender-disaggregated data into evaluation tools. In this way, broad principles can be converted into more tangible practices, enabling gender considerations to be embedded in everyday activities, allowing smoother, consistent and impactful policy execution.

- **Feed structured evidence into policy cycles.**

Living Labs generate context-rich insights from experimentation and co-creation activities, revealing how gender norms, user needs and systemic barriers interact with innovation processes. By synthesising this learning into structured evidence (e.g. case studies, implementation guidelines), Living Labs can inform future research and innovation programming. This input can shape changes in funding priorities and implementation models. The iterative nature of Living Labs experimentation allows for continuous feedback loops, supporting the responsiveness and relevance of policy frameworks over time.

- **Build cross-border alliances that diffuse gender-responsive practices and foster joint learning across territories.**

The ENOLL Network and other cross-regional partnerships provide channels for sharing gender-responsive tools, methods and governance models in order to compare experiences, jointly develop solutions and accelerate the scaling of successful practices. Cross-border collaboration also supports mutual capacity-building, encouraging organisations with less experience to adopt proven approaches and access peer support. By disseminating lessons internationally, Living Labs help align gender-responsive innovation efforts across Europe and beyond, fostering cohesion and avoiding fragmentation in implementation.

- **Engage with relevant stakeholders and authorities to mainstream approaches for gender equality, diversity and inclusion based on Living Labs into regional and national innovation agendas.**

Living Labs can build structured relationships with a range of actors across the quadruple helix – including municipal, regional and national authorities, civil society organisations, academia and private sector stakeholders – to integrate gender-responsive practices into territorial priorities. Through advisory roles, co-design processes and joint experimentation, Living Labs can help embed gender equality, diversity and inclusion principles into Smart Specialisation Strategies, digital and green transition initiatives, and social innovation programmes. This strengthens the legitimacy and sustainability of gender-inclusive innovation policies, ensuring that they respond to societal needs while supporting systemic change at multiple levels. The ENOLL Working Group on Gender in Innovation, established as an outcome of GILL, reinforces this role of Living Labs by promoting collective action and providing a space for knowledge exchange.

The evidence base for policy development

Insights from Action-Oriented Experimentations (AOEs)

The 15 **Action-Oriented Experimentations** developed and implemented within the **GILL project** offered an invaluable opportunity to test, refine and validate gender-responsive innovation methodologies in diverse real-world contexts across Europe. Each AOE functioned as **Living Labs** exploring how gender-responsive smart innovation and entrepreneurship (GRSIE) tools could be integrated into everyday practices, decision-making structures and innovation processes, by applying the **GRSIE framework** to transform internal cultures, processes and everyday practices. These experimentations were implemented in highly varied institutional and sectoral settings from science centres and local administrations to technology companies, research institutes and universities, demonstrating the versatility and transferability of GILL's methods.

Each AOE followed an **iterative four-phase process** of understanding the problem, co-creating interventions, implementing actions and evaluating outcomes. This cyclical approach enabled continuous learning and the contextual adaptation of methods, ensuring that interventions remained relevant and effective. The overall experience revealed that **meaningful and sustainable inclusion cannot be achieved by treating gender equality as an external add-on**, but rather by embedding it within the organisational fabric, decision-making processes and design cycles.

Across the AOEs, a variety of GILL methods were employed to achieve this transformation. Tools such as **Fair Meetings**, **Hear the Right Voices**, **Reflective Diaries**, **Team Manifestos**, **Stop–Start–Continue Workshops**, **Journey Mapping** and **GenderMag** supported self-reflection, collaborative learning and the translation of abstract equity principles into concrete actions. Through these methods, teams were able to recognise patterns of bias, foster mutual understanding and integrate inclusivity into their daily professional environments.

Some AOEs used GILL tools in innovative ways that went beyond their initial purpose, for example, adapting 'Stop–Start–Continue' or 'Hear the Right Voices' to facilitate internal reflection sessions or consultations with external stakeholders, such as experts, citizens and user groups. This flexibility proved to be one of the project's greatest strengths, showing how simple, well-designed tools can be adapted to vastly different contexts, from transport research to software development and from municipal governance to public exhibitions.

The experimentations also showed that the **success of gender-responsive innovation depends largely on organisational commitment**. Where leadership actively supported the process and where adequate time and resources were allocated, the interventions had a deeper and more lasting impact. The methods proved **adaptable and scalable**, being successfully applied across a wide range of disciplines, organisational types and project goals.

Feedback from AOE teams also indicated that contextual conditions, such as team motivation, organisational culture and access to resources, played a decisive role in the extent of transformation achieved. Some methods required complementary strategies to strengthen intersectional awareness, ensuring that gender was addressed in connection with other dimensions of diversity such as age, ability and socioeconomic background.

Examples highlight the diversity of approaches taken. In Denmark, **Experimentarium** transformed its institutional culture by embedding inclusive design and professional development practices into exhibition creation and staff training. In Romania, the **Municipality of Alba Iulia** and the **Transilvania IT Cluster** combined public and private sector engagement to integrate gender-sensitive policies and capacity-building measures, while also introducing the concept of '**gender profitability**' into business modelling. In Germany, a feminist living lab at **Heilbronn University** collaborated with a global technology company to develop **Evoking Change Talk**, a method designed to facilitate everyday dialogue about equality and to shift workplace culture from

within. In the United Kingdom, the healthtech research centre **Devices for Dignity (D4D)** applied GILL methods to identify gender bias in innovation pathways and redesign training and engagement materials to promote fairer, more inclusive medical technologies.

Across these cases, GILL methods proved instrumental in linking micro-level behavioural change with broader structural reform. In **Experimentarium**, the introduction of an Inclusion Committee and Universal Design workshops helped institutionalise inclusive thinking, while in **Alba Iulia**, the creation of a harassment prevention mechanism and flexible work policies illustrated how cultural transformation can be grounded in concrete policy measures. Similarly, in the technology sector, behavioural design tools such as **'Evoking Change Talk'** encouraged employees to question everyday biases, while in the healthtech sector, **Gender Impact Assessments** revealed systematic imbalances in research leadership and funding distribution.

Together, these cases demonstrate that **institutional transformation often begins with small but deliberate shifts**: for example, in how meetings are conducted, how teams reflect on their practices, or how decisions are made. Over time, these micro-level adjustments evolve into broader cultural change, reshaping organisational mindsets and creating more inclusive innovation ecosystems. The AOE's thus confirmed that **embedding inclusion within everyday routines and structures** leads to more equitable participation, stronger innovation outcomes and greater institutional resilience.

A further lesson emerging from these experimentations is that **awareness-raising alone is not enough: real change requires self-evaluation, leadership engagement and long-term monitoring to maintain momentum once initial enthusiasm fades**. When inclusivity becomes part of organisational strategy and daily operations, it ceases to depend on individual champions and becomes a shared institutional value.

In summary, the insights gained from the AOE's reaffirm that gender-responsive innovation is most effective when it is co-created, reflexive and embedded at all levels of organisational activity. The living lab approach adopted by GILL has proven a powerful mechanism to turn theoretical concepts of equality and inclusion into tangible, actionable and scalable transformation.

Key findings from impact evaluation (Phase II of D4.2)

The **impact evaluation** of the AOE's provided clear evidence that the implementation of GILL's methodologies has led to measurable progress in integrating gender equality and inclusivity into innovation ecosystems. Drawing on data collected through surveys, interviews and observations, the evaluation examined key performance indicators such as **effectiveness, efficiency, inclusivity, transferability and usability**. The findings confirm that the GILL framework not only enhanced awareness but also produced substantive organisational and cultural changes.

At the **organisational level**, the AOE's fostered significant structural and procedural transformations. Many institutions revised internal policies, redefined leadership roles and established new bodies, like **Inclusion Committees** or cross-departmental **mentorship schemes**, to sustain gender equality as an institutional priority. Embedding inclusive practices directly into everyday workflows, rather than implementing them as parallel or temporary projects, emerged as one of the most effective strategies for achieving lasting results.

Equally important was the focus on **capacity building**. Through training sessions, awareness workshops and self-reflective tools, participants not only developed a deeper understanding of bias and inequality but also gained the practical skills needed to apply inclusive approaches in their daily work. At **Experimentarium**, for example, universal design workshops enhanced the ability of staff to integrate accessibility and diversity into exhibition design. In **Alba Iulia**, targeted training for civil servants strengthened the municipality's institutional competence in gender mainstreaming, while in the **German tech company**, the iterative application of **Evoking Change Talk** normalised everyday discussions about equity, allowing gender fairness to become part of the organisational routine.

The evaluation also revealed the value of long-term engagement and repeated intervention cycles. AOE that completed two full experimental life cycles achieved greater institutional embedding of methods, demonstrating that continuous reflection, feedback and adaptation are essential for sustained change. In several cases, the introduction of monitoring systems and internal evaluation tools (i.e. the SPARK self-assessment instrument) supported this process by tracking progress on inclusivity, diversity and equity indicators.

The AOE also generated broader **cultural and behavioural change**. Methods such as **Reflective Diaries** and **Fair Meetings** encouraged open dialogue, trust and shared accountability, helping teams to challenge established hierarchies and promote mutual respect. These small, repeated actions collectively built a foundation for more equitable collaboration and long-term change.

Beyond individual organisations, several AOE also contributed to **policy-level and ecosystem-wide impacts**. The Romanian case led to new policy proposals addressing flexible work arrangements, harassment prevention and gender-sensitive recruitment, while also raising awareness across the public and private sector through high-level engagement events. Similarly, in the United Kingdom, the work of D4D influenced the redesign of training modules for healthcare innovators and promoted a more inclusive approach to user engagement in healthtech development. These initiatives demonstrated that gender-responsive innovation not only advances equality but also enhances the **quality, efficiency and creativity of innovation processes**.

The evaluation highlighted several critical success factors. **Visible leadership commitment** was essential for legitimising inclusion initiatives and ensuring their continuity. **Ongoing reflection and data collection** enabled evidence-based learning and adaptation. Moreover, **co-creation with internal stakeholders** enhanced ownership and acceptance of new practices, while **intersectional awareness** ensured that interventions addressed the diverse realities of participants. The evaluation also confirmed that **recurring, low-threshold interventions**, integrated in the daily routine, were far more effective than isolated, one-off training events in embedding genuine behavioural change.

Another key finding was that indifference or resistance to gender topics can undermine transformation efforts if not actively addressed. Several AOE stressed the need for visible leadership advocacy, storytelling and the use of data and lived experiences to make the relevance of gender equality tangible and compelling. Without such engagement, inclusion risks remaining fragmented and unsustainable.

In conclusion, the findings demonstrate that the GILL approach has successfully **translated gender equality objectives into concrete institutional practices**. By combining participatory experimentation, reflective learning and systemic embedding, the AOE achieved tangible improvements in awareness, policy frameworks, professional capacity and cultural transformation. The resulting models of **gender-responsive innovation** are not only replicable but also scalable, offering valuable guidance for future European and international initiatives seeking to foster inclusivity and excellence in innovation. Moreover, the evidence collected through these experimentations provides a strong foundation for further research and policy development on how gender responsiveness can enhance innovation performance, organisational resilience and societal impact across Europe.

Summary of stakeholder feedback from interviews

The stakeholder consultation, comprising nearly **30 interviews across the partner's European Union Member States** and an additional **6 interviews in the United States**, was designed to provide an in-depth understanding of the **implementation, awareness and impact of EU policies on gender and innovation**. The study focused on the Health, Green and Digital sectors, which are the primary areas of interest for the GILL project. Interviews were conducted following the **quadruple helix approach**, engaging representatives from **academia, civil society, industry and government**, in order to gather perspectives on the **opportunities and barriers** faced

by women entrepreneurs and the ways in which EU policies are perceived and applied in practice. The research aimed not only to explore the **degree of awareness of gender and innovation policies**, but also to understand how **gender-disaggregated data is collected**, how policies shape innovation processes, and how structural and cultural factors influence women's participation across sectors.

The consultation revealed a persistent **lack of awareness and limited policy literacy** across the innovation ecosystem. Outside a relatively small circle of stakeholders, including officials directly engaged in programme implementation, researchers specialising in gender and entrepreneurship, and women's entrepreneurship organisations, knowledge of EU gender and innovation instruments remains **partial and fragmented**. This knowledge gap has significant implications, as it contributes to the **normalisation of gender-blind innovation**, obscures accountability mechanisms, and diminishes the potential for more equitable and effective innovation processes.

It became evident that **differences in stakeholder responses were determined less by institutional affiliation than by familiarity with gender and innovation policy frameworks**. Stakeholders who were well-informed consistently highlighted the economic, social and organisational consequences of gender gaps, corroborating findings from recent studies and the direct experience of Action-Oriented Experiments conducted under the GILL project.

Across sectors, stakeholders identified a complex set of **structural, cultural and systemic barriers** affecting women's entrepreneurship. Key obstacles include **persistent gender stereotypes and biases** that influence societal expectations and workplace dynamics, **women's perceived lack of self-confidence and competence** and **limited access to funding and investment opportunities**, often exacerbated by opaque assessment procedures and perceived discrimination. Stakeholders also noted the **scarcity of female role models and mentors**, challenges in **balancing work and family responsibilities**, restricted participation in professional networks and decision-making processes, and the **absence of comprehensive gender-disaggregated data**, which further impacts the capacity to guide effective interventions.

Sector-specific barriers were particularly pronounced. In the **Digital and Green sectors**, stakeholders emphasised the dominance of male-driven cultures, which limit the visibility of women innovators and constrain their access to networks and capital. Business models in these sectors frequently reflect male-oriented entrepreneurial norms, while collaborative and socially oriented approaches preferred by women may be undervalued. In the **Health sector**, although the workforce is predominantly female, **men occupy most decision-making positions**, research activities often prioritise the male body as standard and **care-related innovations are undervalued**, despite their growing importance in the expanding care economy. Stakeholders also highlighted the need for **safe spaces and peer-learning environments** to empower women innovators in health and care-related projects.

In general, **when women hold leadership roles within workplaces that remain strongly male-dominated, the surrounding context itself often hinders the development of genuinely inclusive leadership**. The prevailing norms and expectations of such environments tend to subsume the presence of female managers, minimising, if not outright neutralising, the impact of their efforts to foster a more inclusive organisational culture. As a result, even well-intentioned and skilfully enacted initiatives struggle to gain traction, constrained by structural and cultural barriers that reinforce the status quo.

Despite these barriers, the consultation revealed a few **emerging opportunities**. Stakeholders across sectors acknowledged a **growing policy emphasis on gender equality** and the availability of **women-focused programmes and funding schemes**, such as *WomenTechEU*, *Empower* and *Girls Go Circular*. They highlighted the importance of **mentoring and networking initiatives**, **capacity-building programmes** and **public-private partnerships** that can foster more inclusive innovation ecosystems.

In the **Digital sector**, stakeholders identified opportunities stemming from **digital tools and online platforms** that lower entry barriers, the implementation of **hackathons and dedicated programmes for women in**

technology and the growing attention to **intersectional dimensions of inequality**, including race, age and class, beyond gender alone. Initiatives to combat **cyber violence and ensure safe online spaces** were also seen as critical enablers.

In the **Green sector**, stakeholders emphasised that sustainability, social impact and eco-innovation provide compelling **motivations and incentives for women entrepreneurs**. The development of **female networks** and **inclusive cooperative models** in the green economy were cited as mechanisms that favour broader participation.

In the **Health sector**, opportunities were associated with women's **expertise and active engagement in care and community health**, the **rising investment in female-focused health innovations** and the increasing recognition of **women-led community initiatives**. Stakeholders noted that women's contributions to care-related innovation are not only socially valuable but increasingly economically substantial.

Interviews with **US stakeholders** corroborated many of these findings while highlighting a different ecosystem structure. The US innovation landscape, heavily driven by private investment, shows less policy focus on inclusion, yet the **growth of women-only networks and associations of female venture capitalists** provides important mechanisms for supporting women-led ventures. These networks facilitate mentorship, knowledge exchange and strategies for navigating male-dominated innovation environments.

In the area of policy debate, stakeholder feedback further identified three main **challenges for the implementation of gender-sensitive innovation policies**.

The first challenge concerns the **absence of robust, harmonised qualitative and quantitative indicators** and the lack of **integrated monitoring systems**. While EU frameworks such as Horizon Europe and institutional Gender Equality Plans provide guidance, many programmes **lack defined metrics to evaluate impact**, limiting the capacity to assess whether women's participation translates into decision-making power, agency or innovation quality.

The second challenge is the uneven awareness and recognition of gender–innovation dynamics within the innovation ecosystem. While gender equality policymakers may acknowledge the importance of innovation, actors in start-ups, innovation centres and investment networks often perceive ecosystems as meritocratic and neutral, underestimating the need for targeted inclusion measures. Only when confronted with **gender-disaggregated data** do many stakeholders recognise the potential economic and social benefits of broader participation. This highlights the need for a **business case narrative** complementing the social justice argument, demonstrating that **gender diversity enhances profitability, scalability and market reach**.

The third challenge relates to the **fragmented adoption of gender-sensitive methodologies and tools**. Isolated initiatives, such as bias-awareness workshops, short-term training sessions and evaluative checklists, exist but few innovation centres or Living Labs implement **systematic, long-term strategies**. This is compounded by **limited financial and human resources** and the **male-dominated structure of venture capital**, which constrains women's access to investment and limits the development of scalable, profitable gendered innovations. Stakeholders also noted that women's comparatively cautious approaches to risk may contribute to **long-term sustainability**, challenging conventional investment perceptions.

Stakeholders consistently highlighted the need for **integrated monitoring frameworks**, systematic **collection and dissemination of gender-disaggregated data** and the creation of **safe spaces and peer-learning environments**. Structured mentoring programmes with an **intersectional and intergenerational approach** were recommended to enhance knowledge exchange, leadership development and networking.

The consultation further emphasised that Europe currently **lacks a coherent gender and innovation ecosystem**, in which gender equality actors and innovation stakeholders collaborate to define **new narratives, methodologies and tools**. This gap, however, represents a **strategic opportunity** to design **data-driven, systemic and collaborative frameworks** linking gender equality with competitiveness, scalability and inclusion.

By fostering such an ecosystem, the EU can advance innovation that is **equitable, resilient and sustainable**, while simultaneously achieving **technological and social excellence**.

Validation activities and triangulation of results

The validation of activities and triangulation of results within the GILL project were achieved through a multilayered process that combined evidence from Action-Oriented Experimentations, impact evaluation and stakeholder consultations. The AOE's served as living laboratories to test and refine gender-responsive innovation methodologies in diverse organisational and sectoral contexts across Europe. Their iterative design, comprising phases of understanding, co-creation, implementation and evaluation, ensured that findings were grounded in practical experience and continuously validated through reflection and adaptation.

The impact evaluation, based on data from surveys, interviews and observations, further substantiated the effectiveness and transferability of GILL's methods by assessing key indicators such as inclusivity, efficiency and organisational transformation. Results from different AOE's were cross-compared, revealing consistent patterns of institutional change, from the establishment of Inclusion Committees to the integration of gender-sensitive tools in daily operations.

Complementing this empirical validation, the stakeholder consultations across EU Member States and the United States provided an external lens to interpret and corroborate project findings. These interviews and policy debates confirmed the systemic relevance of GILL's methodologies and identified convergent challenges, such as limited awareness, fragmented implementation and a lack of harmonised indicators, while highlighting emerging opportunities for scaling inclusive innovation.

Together, these triangulated sources ensured that conclusions drawn from the AOE's were not isolated but reflected coherent, evidence-based insights across organisational, cultural and policy dimensions. Given the significant experimentation and validation methodologies, the tools developed within the GILL project can be scaled up and adapted to specific contexts. This approach offers the added advantage of allowing comparison between the outcomes in these specific contexts and the experimentation carried out and documented by the project, while also drawing on GILL's experience to provide guidance for addressing gaps.

Policy recommendations framework

Conceptual anchors: GRSIE, cultural fix and intersectionality

Drawing on the findings of the ERAC Standing Working Group on Gender in Research and Innovation (SWG GRI, 2018–2019), GILL recognises that implicit biases and normative assumptions continue to hinder progress beyond the formal adoption of gender-sensitive tools such as Gender Equality Plans (GEPs). To address these challenges, GILL introduces three interrelated conceptual anchors – the GRSIE framework (Gender-Responsive Smart Innovation and Entrepreneurship), the Cultural Fix and intersectionality – which together provide a multidimensional lens for transformative institutional and cultural change.

The GRSIE framework extends gender mainstreaming into the domains of innovation and entrepreneurship. It promotes inclusive and gender-responsive approaches to innovation processes, ensuring equal access to resources, technologies and funding. GRSIE operates across the macro (structural), meso (institutional) and micro (practice) levels, embedding gender equality into the entire innovation ecosystem and fostering environments that value diverse perspectives and leadership models.

In the context of GILL, GRSIE is defined as a holistic and disruptive response to ‘one-sided innovations’ that privilege technological or market efficiency over social inclusion. ‘Smartness’ is understood not only in relation to digital or technical capacity, but as a mindset and methodological perspective that integrates social and gender responsiveness into all stages of innovation. Gender-responsive smartness therefore requires new modes of collaboration, co-creation and learning that make innovation ecosystems more inclusive, participatory and equitable.

The Cultural Fix represents GILL’s expansion of the ‘three fixes’ approach of the Gendered Innovations framework (participation, excellence and knowledge). It targets the normative and symbolic dimensions of organisations, addressing the cultural pillars that shape values, behaviours and decision-making in R&I ecosystems. The Cultural Fix is thus the *enabling condition* for GRSIE: it provides the cultural environment, norms and practices that allow gender-responsive smart innovation and entrepreneurship to take root and persist over time.

In this sense, **GRSIE operationalises what GILL defines as the ‘Fourth Fix’** of the Gendered Innovations framework – the Cultural Fix – by embedding gender responsiveness and intersectional inclusivity into innovation ecosystems and by addressing the organisational and behavioural norms that either enable or constrain smart, inclusive entrepreneurship. The Fourth Fix therefore represents both a theoretical and practical bridge: it translates cultural change into innovation practice and uses innovation practice as a lever for sustained cultural transformation.

GILL uses a cycle of co-creation and iterative learning, structured around four phases – understand, co-design, implement and evaluate – that are repeated twice to ensure feedback loops between practice and reflection. As already stressed, within this cycle, **15 Action-Oriented Experimentations** across 8 European countries function as living laboratories where the Cultural Fix and GRSIE are co-developed and validated in real-world settings. The AOE test how changes in language, teamwork, leadership styles and organisational processes – for instance, replacing gendered job titles or improving inclusivity in meetings – can concretely advance GRSIE outcomes.

Intersectionality functions as a transversal principle connecting GRSIE and the Cultural Fix. By accounting for the multiple and intersecting dimensions of inequality – including gender, race, class and other social markers – intersectionality ensures that GILL’s interventions move beyond binary gender perspectives. It provides an analytical and operational frame to understand how overlapping identities shape experiences in innovation and entrepreneurship, informing more inclusive and just policy designs.

Together, these conceptual anchors constitute the foundation of GILL’s transformative agenda. They support a shift from compliance-oriented gender equality mechanisms toward systemic cultural transformation,

redefining innovation as a socially inclusive and gender-just process.

The framework directly contributes to the objectives of the **European Research Area (ERA)** and the **Horizon Europe Strategic Plan**, which call for the integration of gender equality and inclusiveness as cross-cutting principles in R&I. It operationalises the commitments of the **EU Gender Equality Strategy 2020–2025** by fostering structural change in organisations and aligning with ERA Policy Agenda Action 5 ('Promote gender equality and foster inclusiveness, diversity and intersectionality in R&I').

Moreover, by addressing the cultural dimension of innovation ecosystems, GILL advances the broader EU ambition to ensure that research and innovation contribute to fair and resilient societies under the 'Europe fit for the Digital and Green Transitions' priority and provides – through interconnecting GRSIE, the Cultural Fix and intersectionality – a coherent and operational framework for embedding gender justice in innovation systems, supporting the long-term EU vision of an inclusive, just and excellent European Research Area.

Scope and intended impact

As already stressed in the paragraphs above, the GILL project seeks to create lasting structural and cultural change within the European innovation ecosystem by embedding gender responsiveness and intersectional inclusivity into entrepreneurship, research and policy processes. Its scope extends beyond formal compliance with gender equality instruments – such as Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) – towards fostering **Gender-Responsive Smart Innovation and Entrepreneurship (GRSIE)** as a guiding principle for sustainable, inclusive and fair innovation practices. GILL thus contributes to the development of the so-called **Fourth Fix**, or Cultural Fix, which addresses the underlying organisational and normative conditions that either enable or impede gender-responsive smartness in innovation ecosystems.

The project's intended impact is twofold. First, it aims to strengthen the evidence base and methodological capacity for gender-responsive innovation through a set of **Action-Oriented Experimentations (AOEs)** implemented across Europe. These AOEs act as living laboratories for testing how gender-aware design, inclusive leadership and participatory methods can transform organisational routines, product development cycles and entrepreneurial environments. Second, GILL seeks to translate these empirical insights into actionable tools, methods and policy recommendations that can be scaled and sustained through a pan-European hub for gender-responsive innovation.

The **Impact Evaluation** framework examines the contribution of GILL measures to advancing gender equality in entrepreneurship and innovation. It assesses both the **extent and nature of change** achieved – for example, improvements in inclusivity in meetings, shifts in the use of gender-neutral language, or enhanced awareness of gender bias in decision-making – and the **mechanisms through which these changes occur**, such as organisational learning or policy reform. The evaluation also explores how GILL's interventions interact with external influences, identifying the combination of cultural, institutional and behavioural factors that contribute to observed outcomes.

Complementing this, the **Process Evaluation** investigates *how* interventions have been designed and implemented within the AOEs. It analyses the enablers and barriers encountered throughout the innovation cycle, including time constraints, information gaps, institutional inertia and stakeholder engagement dynamics. By capturing lessons from both successful and less successful implementations, this evaluation provides critical feedback to improve tools, communication processes and participatory mechanisms. Together, these evaluation dimensions ensure that GILL's approach remains adaptive, reflexive and evidence-based.

Within this framework, the project's **specific areas of intended impact** include:

1. **Identifying and overcoming impediments to GRSIE** by exposing cultural and procedural barriers to equality in innovation ecosystems.

2. **Developing and validating practical tools and methods** to enact the Cultural Fix, leading to more inclusive teamwork, leadership models and innovation practices.
3. **Demonstrating the systemic benefits of GRSIE**, including improved innovation quality, diversified participation and reducing gender and diversity gaps.
4. **Strengthening dissemination and communication pathways** to ensure broad awareness, replication and policy uptake of project outcomes across sectors and governance levels.

Recognising that transformative change requires favourable enabling conditions, GILL also addresses several **external barriers to impact** identified in the project's Description of Action. These include a potential lack of stakeholder interest, institutional resistance to organisational transformation, and economic constraints affecting the sustainability of follow-up actions. To mitigate these, GILL employs context-sensitive dissemination strategies to tailor messages and tools to local realities, demonstrates the technological, economic and social value of GRSIE and establishes strategy and business plans to secure the long-term viability of its pan-European hub.

For example, **AOE2 ('Brick by Brick')** explored how female academics could be better supported in transforming research into entrepreneurial initiatives by creating a digital 'innovation bridge' platform tailored to their needs and professional narratives. This experiment not only tested practical tools for enabling women's engagement with technology transfer offices but also examined cultural barriers in academia that prevent women from viewing themselves as entrepreneurs.

In **AOE3**, GILL methodologies were embedded into the *Devices for Dignity (D4D)* programme to make healthcare innovation cycles more gender-responsive. Ten practitioner-innovators integrated GILL tools in the design of new medical devices, demonstrating how gender-sensitive approaches could enhance patient outcomes and inclusivity in health technology entrepreneurship.

The **AOE8**, coordinated by *Fondazione Giacomo Brodolini (FGB)*, focused on building the capacity of start-ups and innovation hubs in Lombardy and Valle d'Aosta (Italy) to address gender-related issues in their business models. By piloting GILL outputs within innovation ecosystems, FGB worked with up to 30 companies to test gender-analysis frameworks and participatory tools (GaDAPs, consultations and case studies) that strengthened the integration of gender considerations into design, management and strategic planning. This initiative enhanced the awareness and competence of female entrepreneurs, helping them to read market and technological contexts through a gender lens and to develop innovations that respond more effectively to diverse end-user needs.

Similarly, **AOE13** worked with technology companies to pilot gendered innovation methods in organisational contexts, focusing on how workplace culture, team practices and product design could be reconfigured to retain women in tech and ensure that digital innovations serve diverse populations. These experiments provide tangible evidence of how cultural transformation (the Cultural Fix) and gender-responsive innovation (GRSIE) are intertwined and mutually reinforcing.

The linkage between GRSIE and the Cultural Fix is further reinforced by GILL's dual evaluation strategy. **Impact evaluation** focuses on the tangible changes resulting from the AOE's – such as improvements in inclusivity, organisational awareness and participation in innovation processes – and on understanding why these changes occur. **Process evaluation**, in turn, analyses *how* interventions are implemented and which drivers, barriers and support mechanisms influence their success. Together, these evaluations ensure that cultural transformation (the Cultural Fix) and innovation practice (GRSIE) are mutually reinforcing: the former creates the conditions for inclusive innovation, while the latter provides evidence-based feedback that sustains cultural change.

Principles guiding the recommendations

The recommendations developed within the GILL project and reported in this document are guided by a coherent set of principles that reflect both the project's conceptual framework and the broader objectives of the European Research Area (ERA) and Horizon Europe. These principles – **inclusiveness**, **institutional change** and **scalability** – provide the normative and operational foundation for ensuring that GILL's results are transformative, sustainable and applicable across diverse contexts in innovation and entrepreneurship.

GILL positions inclusiveness as a central pillar of GRSIE. The project challenges the limitations of traditional approaches to inclusivity in research and innovation – such as conventional user-centred design and tokenistic participation models – which often fail to capture the lived experience of diverse user groups or to engage participants as active co-creators. Instead, GILL promotes a systematic and phenomenological approach that recognises diversity as a source of innovation and as a structural condition for excellence.

Through its Action-Oriented Experimentations, GILL interrogates and disrupts existing open innovation (OI) practices, rethinking participation, data gathering and representation so that women and under-represented groups are not merely consulted but actively shape the innovation process. The project thereby strengthens the inclusiveness dimension of the ERA by connecting individuals, institutions and communities through an intersectional and gender-responsive collaboration platform.

This platform and its Living Lab network foster a self-sustaining community that enhances gender equality and diversity in entrepreneurship and innovation, ensuring that no social group is left behind. The resulting recommendations call for embedding inclusiveness not only in specific project activities but also in the mindsets, tools and evaluation criteria used by researchers, entrepreneurs and policymakers across the Quadruple Helix.

Institutional change lies at the heart of GILL's theory of transformation. The project recognises that achieving gender-responsive innovation requires not only individual awareness and technical interventions but also the reconfiguration of organisational cultures, governance structures and value systems that shape innovation practices.

Building on the Cultural Fix, GILL proposes mechanisms to integrate gender and intersectionality into the organisational DNA of R&I institutions, start-ups and public authorities. These mechanisms include the development of new governance models, participatory evaluation tools and tailored capacity-building programmes (KERs 2, 4 and 5) that target both managerial and operational levels.

By promoting reflection-in-action, continuous learning and dynamic capacity building, GILL fosters institutional environments capable of sustaining inclusivity beyond the duration of the project. The dynamic capacity-building model allows for iterative refinement of knowledge, practices and tools after each implementation cycle, ensuring that learning processes remain responsive to evolving social and technological contexts. This approach exemplifies GILL's contribution to institutionalising gender equality as a driver of innovation quality, social responsiveness and organisational resilience within the ERA.

Finally, the GILL methodology has been designed to ensure replicability and scalability across different innovation systems and national contexts. Lessons learned from the AOE's – implemented in eight European countries – demonstrate that gender-responsive innovation practices can be effectively adapted to various sectors, such as academia, health technology, AI, entrepreneurship and governance.

The project's recommendations are therefore conceived with a dual scalability logic: **upward**, to enable policy and institutional adoption at the European level and **outward**, to allow adaptation to new domains and geographical areas beyond the initial implementation sites. Ultimately, scalability in GILL is not limited to the reproduction of tools, but extends to the **diffusion of a transformative culture** – one that values inclusivity, equality and intersectionality as key components of innovation excellence.

In line with these guiding principles, GILL's recommendations aim to embed gender responsiveness and inclusiveness as core criteria for innovation success, promoting institutional transformation and ensuring that the project's methodologies, tools and frameworks can be scaled and sustained to strengthen the inclusiveness and resilience of the European Research Area.

Table 2. Principles guiding GILL's recommendations

Principle	Operational focus	Expected impact on ERA
Inclusiveness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integrate gender and intersectionality across the entire innovation cycle (design, implementation, evaluation). • Replace tokenistic participation with genuine co-creation and representation of diverse stakeholders in Open Innovation Ecosystems (OIEs). • Strengthen collaboration between individuals, institutions and communities through the GILL Living Lab network and digital platform. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Broader participation of under-represented groups in research and innovation. • Enhanced inclusivity and social responsiveness in the European Research and Innovation system. • Creation of a self-sustaining, gender-responsive innovation community supporting ERA's inclusiveness dimension.
Institutional Change	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Apply the 'Fourth Fix' (Cultural Fix) to transform organisational norms, governance models and learning processes. • Develop dynamic capacity-building programmes and participatory evaluation mechanisms to embed gender responsiveness in institutional practice. • Strengthen managerial and operational capacities for gender-smart decision-making and policy integration. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Structural and cultural transformation within R&I institutions and start-ups. • Institutionalisation of gender equality as a quality dimension of innovation. • Greater organisational resilience and adaptability to social and technological change across ERA.
Scalability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adapt and replicate GILL methodologies across different sectors, geographies and innovation systems. • Promote upward scaling (policy adoption at EU level) and outward scaling (adaptation to new domains). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased uptake of gender-responsive innovation practices at European and national levels. • Strengthened cross-sectoral collaboration and knowledge transfer. • Long-term sustainability of inclusive innovation ecosystems within ERA.

Thematic policy recommendations

Cross-cutting recommendations

These recommendations apply across sectors, funding frameworks and institutional contexts.

1. Integrate Living Lab methodologies into Gender Equality Plans (GEPs)

- Embed Living Lab approaches in all stages of GEPs: diagnosis, design, implementation and evaluation.
- Use participatory methods to involve diverse stakeholders in co-creating and testing gender equality measures.
- Pilot interventions in real organisational contexts, gather evidence and adapt policies based on feedback.
- Establish structured feedback loops to translate lessons from pilots into broader institutional strategies.
- Allocate resources and build capacity for staff to manage participatory processes effectively.

2. Align Horizon Europe GEPs with ERA Actions

- Integrate GILL insights and Cultural Fix indicators into Horizon Europe GEPs and ERA Action 5 frameworks.
- Treat GEP activities as drivers of institutional innovation, not just compliance obligations.
- Facilitate peer-learning networks across institutions to share validated gender-responsive practices.
- Encourage evidence-based refinement of both policy and practice through systematic evaluation.

3. Institutionalise the Cultural Fix model

- Adopt the Cultural Fix framework to address norms, behaviours and routines within institutions.
- Define measurable cultural indicators such as inclusivity in meetings, participatory governance and reflective practices.
- Incorporate cultural indicators into institutional monitoring and performance evaluation.
- Provide practical guidance for leadership to embed inclusive routines in everyday organisational processes.

4. Establish participatory and reflexive governance structures

- Create inclusion committees and cross-department working groups with formal mandates and resources.
- Ensure governance structures integrate gender and intersectionality considerations into decision-making.
- Embed co-creation, reflection and feedback loops into organisational processes to foster collective ownership of equality objectives.
- Require transparent reporting and accountability mechanisms for decisions and outcomes.

5. Incentivise leadership commitment and behavioural change

- Link leadership evaluation and institutional funding to demonstrate progress on gender equality.
- Integrate gender equality objectives into institutional missions and key performance indicators.
- Support leadership development programmes with practical tools for inclusive decision-making.

6. Embed continuous learning and reflective monitoring

- Require systematic use of self-assessment tools, reflective diaries and gender-disaggregated data to track progress.
- Encourage evidence-based adjustment of policies and measures based on monitoring results.
- Facilitate institutional learning by documenting best practices and lessons learned.
- Promote peer feedback and cross-institutional exchange of reflective insights.

7. Develop harmonised, co-created monitoring frameworks

- Establish EU-wide monitoring systems combining quantitative and qualitative indicators to ensure the effectiveness of the actions implemented and, if needed, the ability to define and implement changes.
- Co-create indicators with stakeholders to ensure their relevance, comparability and adaptability.
- Use monitoring outputs to inform policy adaptation and drive systemic improvements.
- Encourage consistent reporting and transparency across institutions.

8. Introduce systemic incentives and conditionality

- Link access to funding and institutional resources to demonstrable gender equality outcomes.
- Integrate inclusive procurement and investment criteria into eligibility and evaluation processes.
- Make gender-disaggregated reporting mandatory and tie compliance to future funding.
- Support organisations with technical assistance to meet systemic requirements.

9. Scale successful Action-Oriented Experimentations (AOEs)

- Implement AOEs such as 'Fair Meetings,' 'Stop-Start-Continue,' and 'Evoking Change Talk' across institutions.
- Create a European repository of validated AOEs to enable knowledge sharing and standardisation.
- Facilitate peer-learning and capacity-building through networks like the ENoLL Working Group.
- Encourage adaptation of AOEs to diverse organisational contexts while preserving core principles.

10. Strengthen interdisciplinary collaboration to address bias in research and living labs

- Funding incentives: Prioritise projects that explicitly budget for interdisciplinary teams (developers, sociologists and gender experts) and that include co-created evaluation plans.
- Pilot lab networks: Seed networks of labs that bring technical and social expertise together to co-develop data sets, evaluation metrics and governance protocols.
- Open data sets and methods: Support the creation of privacy-respecting, well-documented data sets that are curated to minimise gender and intersectional bias and are available for benchmarking.
- Toolkits for practitioners: Publish practical toolkits (checklists, code snippets, evaluation scripts) that teams can adopt to test algorithmic fairness and deploy mitigations.

Recommendations for digital innovation ecosystems

11. Require gender impact assessments for AI and digitalisation projects

- Mandate gender and intersectional impact assessments at proposal, mid-term and final stages of R&I projects.
- Ensure assessments evaluate algorithmic bias, representation in data sets and governance structures.
- Encourage interdisciplinary teams including technical and social science expertise.
- Link compliance with ethical and inclusive standards to funding eligibility and scoring.

12. Implement inclusive digital design standards and training

- Integrate inclusive design principles into EU and national digital innovation standards.
- Train developers and engineers on gender, intersectionality and participatory design methods.
- Promote Living Labs as environments for testing inclusive products and services in ICT and AI.
- Establish certification or recognition schemes for digital solutions meeting inclusive design criteria.

13. Strengthen collaboration to address gender bias in technology

- Fund interdisciplinary collaboration among developers, social scientists and gender experts.
- Encourage open, bias-aware data sets and transparent algorithmic design.
- Provide practical toolkits and templates to operationalise gender fairness in digital innovation projects.
- Foster knowledge exchange and diffusion of inclusive practices across organisations.

Recommendations for green transition and sustainability

14. Apply gender and intersectional impact assessments in climate and energy policy

- **Mandatory GIAs in green funds:** Require gender and intersectional impact assessments for projects funded by the Green Deal, Just Transition Fund and national green programmes. Assessments must consider energy poverty, access to jobs, distributional effects and care responsibilities.
- **Design of reskilling and upskilling programmes:** Insist that reskilling and upskilling programmes include gender-responsive outreach, flexible formats (e.g. part-time, online) and support services (e.g. childcare stipends) to enable participation of women and marginalised groups.
- **Policy design templates:** Provide standard templates and example GIAs tailored to green projects to help implementers identify likely gendered impacts and mitigation strategies.
- **Monitoring and targeting:** Include gender-disaggregated employment metrics and access to finance indicators in green programme monitoring to inform adaptive policy (e.g. correct under-representation in a timely manner).
- **Community engagement:** Require participatory needs assessments with affected communities (including women's groups) before approving large, medium and small infrastructure projects.

15. Support women entrepreneurs in green tech and social innovation

- **Dedicated funding lines:** Create targeted grants, blended finance instruments and procurement quotas for women-led green ventures with clear eligibility and transparent application support.
- **Mentoring and networks:** Fund mentorship programmes linking women founders to investors, technical partners and procurement officers; create matchmaking events with public buyers.
- **Capacity building:** Offer tailored business development training on scaling, investment readiness, regulatory pathways and tendering for public contracts. Provide modular, time-flexible formats.
- **Visibility and procurement channels:** Use public procurement to create demonstration contracts for women-led ventures and promote success stories to mobilise private investment.
- **Metrics for impact:** Require reporting on both environmental performance and gender outcomes (jobs created for women, leadership representation) as part of funding agreements.

16. Promote equity and leadership for women in green entrepreneurship

- **Targeted incubators:** Establish incubators and accelerator tracks specifically for women-led green start-ups, offering tailored mentorship, environmental compliance support, life-cycle assessment guidance and investor introductions in the sectors of climate tech, energy transition and the circular economy.
- **Inclusive investment criteria:** Encourage public and private funders to integrate gender equality and sustainability impact into investment scoring and to report systematically on the gender balance of funded green ventures and leadership teams.
- **Procurement pathways:** Create procurement channels reserved or prioritised for inclusive green innovations developed by diverse teams, particularly in renewable energy, waste management, sustainable infrastructure and climate adaptation.
- **Role models and visibility:** Run communication campaigns, award schemes and speaker series showcasing women leaders in green innovation and environmental entrepreneurship to build

visibility and strengthen professional ecosystems.

- **Monitoring leadership outcomes:** Require reporting on gender balance in leadership, ownership structures and career progression within funded green innovation programmes and sustainability initiatives.

Recommendations for health innovation

17. Integrate sex- and gender-sensitive methods into health R&I

- **Mandatory design requirements:** Require health R&I proposals (clinical trials, medtech, digital health) to include sex- and gender-sensitive protocols: stratified sampling, sex-disaggregated analysis and gender-relevant endpoints.
- **Methodological guidance:** Publish concrete methodological guidance (how to power studies for sex differences, how to measure gendered effects) and expect applicants to justify omission if not applicable.
- **Cross-disciplinary consortia:** Fund consortia that combine clinicians, engineers, social scientists and gender specialists to ensure technologies address diverse needs across the life course and care contexts.
- **Regulatory and procurement incentives:** Tie public procurement and regulatory fast-track options to demonstrated gender-sensitive validation and inclusive usability testing.
- **Data governance:** Mandate transparent data collection practices and disaggregated reporting, with safeguards for privacy and ethics when dealing with sensitive demographic attributes.

18. Promote equity and leadership for women in health entrepreneurship

- **Targeted incubators:** Establish incubators and accelerator tracks specifically for women-led health tech start-ups, offering tailored mentorship, clinical validation support and investor introductions.
- **Inclusive investment criteria:** Encourage public and private funders to include diversity and social-impact dimensions in investment scoring and to report on portfolio gender balance.
- **Procurement pathways:** Create procurement windows reserved or prioritised for inclusive health innovations developed by diverse teams to create market pull.
- **Role models and visibility:** Run visibility campaigns and speaker series showcasing women leaders in health innovation to stimulate networks and aspirational pipelines.
- **Monitoring leadership outcomes:** Require reporting on leadership gender balance and career progression metrics for funded health innovation programmes.

Institutional and cultural transformation tools

19. Institutionalise reflexivity, participatory governance and co-creation

- **Reflexive practices in routine work:** Require research units to embed short reflexive practices (e.g. 10-minute reflective agenda item after major decisions, reflective diaries for project leads) and report uptake.
- **Co-creation process standards:** Provide a standard operating procedure for co-creation: stakeholder mapping, inclusion criteria, facilitation roles, documentation requirements and how outputs feed into

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governance.

- **Inclusion committees with mandate:** Ensure committees have the authority to propose changes to hiring, procurement and research strategies and to require responses from leadership within set time frames.
- **Capacity investment:** Fund dedicated staff time (e.g. a GEP coordinator, trained facilitators) so participatory processes are sustained and not ad hoc.
- **Documentation and diffusion:** Require short public syntheses of co-creation outputs and roadmaps for implementation so other units can replicate successful measures.

20. Embed continuous learning and reflective monitoring mechanisms for gender equality

- **Self-evaluation tools:** Mandate the use of tools like SPARK self-evaluation and reflective diaries at defined intervals (annual SPARK, quarterly reflective checkpoints) to generate practice-level learning.
- **Mixed evidence cycles:** Require short learning cycles where qualitative reflections and quantitative indicators are jointly used to adapt actions every 6 to 12 months.
- **Peer review and learning networks:** Set up inter-institutional learning groups that review each other's SPARK outputs, offer constructive feedback and share tested solutions.
- **Public accountability:** Publish anonymised learning summaries and change logs to demonstrate institutional learning and maintain public trust.
- **Capacity for evaluation:** Invest in training staff to conduct and interpret reflective monitoring and to turn insights into concrete policy adjustments.

Conclusions and outlook

Summary of strategic impact

The strategic impact of the GILL project lies in its ability to translate conceptual frameworks, EU policy priorities and methodological innovations into tangible organisational and cultural transformation across diverse innovation ecosystems. The combined evidence from AOE, impact evaluation and stakeholder consultations demonstrates that inclusive and gender-responsive innovation is most effective when approached as a systemic endeavour operating simultaneously at structural, institutional and behavioural levels.

Through the GRSIE framework, the Cultural Fix and intersectional analysis, GILL shows how gender equality can evolve from a procedural requirement to a driver of excellence, competitiveness and resilience within the European R&I landscape. The project validated that interventions such as Fair Meetings, Reflective Diaries, Hear the Right Voices, Gender Impact Assessments and Evoking Change Talk can reshape decision-making processes, enhance everyday reflexivity and support the internalisation of inclusive behaviours. These iterative, low-threshold methods foster shared accountability, strengthen organisational learning and enable durable cultural change across sectors including health, digital, technology and public administration.

A key strategic contribution concerns the role of Living Labs, which emerged as effective infrastructures for implementing EU gender agendas in real-life settings. Living Labs demonstrate that inclusive innovation requires structural, procedural and cultural mechanisms enabling diverse actors to participate in shared decision-making. By implementing EU agendas and strategies on gender equality within real-life contexts, they can uncover practical barriers, power dynamics and enablers experienced by citizens, organisations and territories.

This grounded evidence can be channelled back to policymakers, strengthening the design of future R&I frameworks – such as FP10 – alongside national innovation strategies. GILL can support this process by offering actionable gender-responsive methods, a structured portfolio of tools tested through the Action-Oriented Experimentations, a working group space that can enhance standardisation and knowledge sharing and dedicated capacity-building instruments. These contributions empower Living Labs to evolve their governance and operational models while reinforcing the connection between institutional transformation, policy design and societal needs.

Ultimately, the strategic impact of GILL lies in its capacity to bridge the gap between policy ambition and practical implementation. It provides evidence-based pathways to strengthen Gender Equality Plans, improve monitoring and evaluation, enhance cross-sectoral collaboration and operationalise the EU Gender Equality Strategy, Horizon Europe requirements and ERA objectives. By demonstrating the scalability and transferability of its methods across diverse organisational contexts, the project establishes a robust foundation for future European initiatives seeking to align gender equality, innovation excellence and sustainable development.

Next steps and future engagement with policymakers

The next phase of the GILL Policy Development Strategy builds on this consolidated evidence to reinforce structured collaboration with policymakers at EU, national, regional and local levels. Future engagement will focus on embedding gender-responsive innovation into upcoming policy cycles – including FP10, the post-2025 EU Gender Equality Strategy and the evolution of Horizon Europe's GEP eligibility criterion – by ensuring that these frameworks benefit from the empirical insights generated through AOE, impact evaluation and stakeholder consultations. Strengthening monitoring mechanisms, harmonising indicators and enhancing

accountability structures will be central priorities, given the persistent challenges identified in the report, such as uneven policy implementation, limited policy literacy, fragmented data collection and conceptual ambiguities around gender-responsive innovation.

GILL will also contribute to the creation of a more coherent European gender and innovation ecosystem, addressing the gap revealed through interviews with stakeholders across the Quadruple Helix. This includes promoting integrated monitoring approaches, fostering data-driven governance and supporting the systematic use of gender-disaggregated data in innovation processes. Engagement with policymakers will emphasise the importance of reflexive governance, participatory approaches and continuous learning cycles, building on the demonstrated value of SPARK self-assessment, co-creation standards, Inclusion Committees, universal design practices and reflective monitoring mechanisms. These elements collectively contribute to making gender equality a shared organisational value rather than an isolated project.

Future collaboration will also involve facilitating knowledge exchange, strengthening inter-institutional learning networks and supporting policymaking processes with grounded evidence from Living Labs. As Europe prepares for major transformations linked to digitalisation, the green transition, strategic autonomy and health system innovation, GILL's findings offer concrete guidance for integrating gender and intersectional perspectives into these domains. By continuing to provide tested tools, capacity-building activities and validated methodologies, the project aims to ensure that policymakers can design and implement more inclusive, context-sensitive and effective innovation policies. Through sustained engagement and iterative dialogue, GILL will reinforce Europe's capacity to align competitiveness with social justice and to advance innovation ecosystems that are gender-responsive, culturally inclusive and socially sustainable.

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